

Statistical analysis plan: emulation of a target trial in DEVOTE using the National Diabetes Audit

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Overview of DEVOTE study

The DEVOTE trial was a treat-to-target, randomised, double-blind, active comparator-controlled study which evaluated the cardiovascular safety of insulin Degludec in patients with type 2 diabetes (1). The trial was conducted at 438 sites in 20 countries and was designed to continue until the occurrence of at least 633 primary outcome events. A total of 7,637 patients were randomly assigned to receive either insulin degludec (n=3,818) or insulin glargine (n=3,819) once daily, in addition to usual care. Of those who were randomised, 6,509 (85.2%) of patients had established cardiovascular disease (CVD) and/or chronic kidney disease (CKD) at baseline, the mean age was 65 years, the mean duration of diabetes was 16.4 years, the mean HbA1c was 8.5+/-1.7% and 84% were receiving insulin.

Primary Outcome

The primary composite outcome was the first occurrence of a major cardiovascular event (death from CVD, non-fatal myocardial infarction or non-fatal stroke), with a pre-specified non-inferiority margin of 1.3.

Secondary Outcomes

The secondary outcomes were the number and incidence of severe hypoglycaemia, an expanded composite CVD outcome (the primary composite outcome or unstable angina leading to hospitalisation), time from randomisation to death from any cause, serious adverse events or adverse events leading to discontinuation of the intervention, levels of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) and fasting plasma glucose, blood pressure, pulse, lipid measurements, weight, body-mass index, estimated glomerular filtration rate, nocturnal severe hypoglycaemia and basal and bolus insulin dose.

Key findings

The primary outcome occurred in 325 (8.5%) patients in the degludec group and 356 (9.3%) patients in the glargine group (HR: 0.91, CI: 0.78-1.06) (for non-inferiority, P<0.001). At 24 months, the mean HbA1c was 7.5+/-1.2% in each group while the fasting plasma was significantly lower in the degludec group compared to the glargine group (128+/-56 vs 136 +/-57). Hypoglycaemia occurred in 187 (4.9%) patients in the degludec group and 252 (6.6%) in the glargine group. There was no difference in the rate of adverse events between the two groups.

Conclusion

Degludec was non-inferior to glargine with respect to the incidence of major CVD events.

1. Trial Emulation Study Design

1.1. Study population

In England, the NHS provides health care, free at the point of administration. We will use the National Diabetes Audit (NDA) to evaluate the cardiovascular disease outcomes of degludec in individuals with type 2 diabetes. The NDA was established in 2003 and was developed to assess the quality of, and variation in, diabetes clinical care and outcomes across England for individuals with diabetes. From 2017, NDA data have been collected by the General Practice Extraction System, a national automated process that extracts data from primary care electronic patient records and from 2017/18 onwards, over 98% of general practices in England have provided data to the NDA. In addition, specialist secondary care health providers submit data extracts via a secure Clinical Audit Platform and from 2019/20, data on digital retinal screening have been submitted by the NHS Diabetes Eye screening programme. Data extracted include demographic data (e.g., age, sex, ethnicity, age at diagnosis and deprivation), clinical data (e.g. HbA1c measurements, blood pressure, cholesterol and body mass index) and from 2017/18, diabetes-related medication (glucose-lowering medications, antihypertensive medications and statins). Each audit period covers 15 months from 1 January in the first year to 31 March in the second year. The NDA will be linked by pseudo-NHS number to civil death registrations collated by the Office for National Statistics and hospital episode statistics (HES) which contains details about hospital admission, out-patient appointments, and attendance to Accident and Emergency departments (Figure 1) (2).

Figure1- Data flows for the National Diabetes Audit

1.2. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

To ensure the DEVOTE trial and the emulated trial using observational data are comparable, we need to establish a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria based on clinical expertise.

Inclusion criteria

Table 1: Proposed Trial Emulation inclusion criteria using the NDA

Trial	Emulation
Type 2 diabetes	Individuals with type 2 diabetes are included in the NDA if they have a valid SNOMED code for type 2 diabetes in their electronic health record. Where there are inconsistencies in the type of diabetes recorded, the most recent type recorded by a specialist diabetes care provider will be used, if available. If the data have not been provided by a specialist diabetes provider, the most recent type of diabetes recorded in primary care will be used.
HbA1c ≥ 7.0 % or HbA1c $< 7.0\%$ and current insulin treatment corresponding to ≥ 20 U/day of basal insulin	Individuals whose latest HbA1c measurement, recorded within one year of start of treatment ≥ 53 mmol/mol (7.0%)
<p>Age ≥ 50 years at screening and at least one of the following conditions prior to inclusion :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prior myocardial infarction - Prior stroke or prior TIA - Prior coronary, carotid or peripheral arterial revascularization - $>50\%$ stenosis on angiography or other imaging of coronary, carotid or lower extremity artery - History of symptomatic coronary heart disease documented by positive exercise stress test or any cardiac imaging, or unstable angina pectoris with ECG changes - Asymptomatic cardiac ischemia documented by positive nuclear imaging test or exercise test or dobutamine stress echo - Chronic heart failure NYHA class II–III 	<p>Individuals aged 50 years or older at the start of each audit period in which treatment starts and at least one admission to hospital over the previous 10 years prior to start of treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - myocardial infarction, - stroke, - revascularization procedure, - angiography procedure, - unstable angina, - heart failure, - chronic kidney disease or an estimated glomerular filtration (eGFR) rate 30-59 recorded in their primary care record* <p>(ICD-10 codes in appendix)</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chronic kidney disease corresponding to estimated glomerular filtration rate 30–59 mL/min/1.73m² per CKD-EPI <p>OR</p> <p>Age ≥60 years at screening and at least one of the following risk factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microalbuminuria or proteinuria - Hypertension and left ventricular hypertrophy by ECG or imaging - Left ventricular systolic and diastolic dysfunction by imaging - Ankle/brachial index <0.9 	<p>OR</p> <p>Individuals aged 60 years or older at the start of each audit period in which treatment starts and at least one admission to hospital over the previous 10 years prior to start of treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hypertension or a record of hypertension in their primary care record OR - anti-hypertensive medication <p>(ICD-10 codes in appendix).</p>
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*Data for Creatinine are not available for 10 years, so we considered the data within 2 years before starting the treatment.

** Throughout the analysis, we define Hypertension as either having a record of Systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 and Diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 , within one year before starting one of the treatments of interest or having been prescribed anti-hypertensive drug within 180 days before starting the treatment.

Exclusion criteria

Table 2: Trial emulation exclusion criteria using the NDA

Trial	Emulation
An acute coronary or cerebrovascular event in the previous 60 days	Admission to hospital with myocardial infarction or stroke within 60 days from start of treatment. ICD-10 codes in appendix
Planned revascularization of coronary, carotid or peripheral arteries.	Not able to measure
Chronic heart failure NYHA IV	Admission to hospital with heart failure within 60 days from start of treatment. ICD-10 codes in appendix
Current haemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis or eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73 m ² per CKD-EPI	An eGFR <30 mL/min up to two years before start of treatment
End-stage liver disease, defined as the presence of	Admission to hospital with liver disease within 60 days

acute or chronic liver disease and recent history of one or more of the following: ascites, encephalopathy, variceal bleeding, bilirubin ≥ 2.0 mg/dL, albumin level ≤ 3.5 g/dL, prothrombin time ≥ 4 seconds prolonged, international normalized ratio ≥ 1.7 or prior liver transplant	from start of treatment. ICD-10 codes in appendix
Known or suspected hypersensitivity to trial products or related products	Not able to measure
Female of child-bearing potential who is pregnant, breast-feeding or intends to become pregnant, or is not using adequate contraceptive methods as required by local law or practice	Not able to measure
Expected simultaneous participation in any other clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product. Participation in a clinical trial with stent(s) is allowed	Not able to measure
Receipt of any investigational medicinal product within 30 days before randomization. Brazil: Receipt of any investigational medicinal product within 1 year before randomization unless there is a direct benefit to the patient at the investigator's discretion	Not able to measure
Current or past (within the last 5 years) malignant neoplasms (except basal cell and squamous cell skin carcinoma)	Admission to hospital with cancer within 5 years from start of treatment. ICD-10 codes in appendix
Any condition that, in the investigator's opinion, would make the patient unable to adhere to the initial trial visit schedule and procedures	Not able to measure

1.3. Study duration and follow up

The emulation timeframe will be from 2017/18 to 2021/22, ensuring a minimum of two year of follow-up.

The index date (time zero) is defined as the first instance when a patient redeems a prescription for one of the pharmacotherapies of interest and meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria within the specified time period. Follow up measurements if available, refer to measurements closest to the middle of the interval.

1.4. Treatment of interest

The aim of trial emulation is primarily to compare continuous treatment with Insulin degludec with continuous treatment with insulin glargine for 1-2 years. We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months, with patients being considered on treatment in a time interval if at least one prescription was redeemed in that interval.

1.5. Outcome(s)

In the DEVOTE trial, the primary composite outcome was the first occurrence of a major cardiovascular event (death from CVD, non-fatal myocardial infarction or non-fatal stroke). The secondary analyses were the number and incidence of severe hypoglycaemia, an expanded composite CVD outcome (the primary composite outcome or unstable angina leading to hospitalisation), time from randomisation to death from any cause, serious adverse events or adverse events leading to discontinuation of the intervention.

Table 3: Primary and secondary outcomes in the DEVOTE trial and emulation study

Trial	Emulation
The primary composite cardiovascular outcome was defined as the first confirmed event of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction or nonfatal stroke.	CVD death or admission to hospital for myocardial infarction or stroke ICD10-codes in appendix
The expanded composite cardiovascular outcome was the first confirmed event of the primary composite cardiovascular outcome with the addition of unstable angina pectoris leading to hospitalization	CVD death myocardial infarction, stroke or unstable angina ICD10-codes in appendix
Death from any cause	Competing event: All cause death
glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) and fasting plasma glucose	Not able to measure
blood pressure	Not able to measure
Pulse	Not able to measure
lipid measurements,	Not able to measure
Weight / body-mass index (BMI),	Not able to measure
estimated glomerular filtration rate	Not able to measure

Potential confounders:

We will consider two groups of variables: pre-treatment variables and time-varying variables. These variables will help control for confounding and ensure a robust comparison between continuous treatment with insulin degludec with continuous treatment with insulin glargine. Pre-treatment and baseline variables will be assessed at baseline or up to 10 years before baseline to control for confounding factors present before treatment initiation. Time-varying variables will be updated throughout the study period to account for changes that may affect treatment outcomes.

Pre-treatment and baseline variable	Time-varying variables
Age (continuous)	
Sex (male, female or unspecified)	
Index of multiple deprivation (calculated from each individual's postcode)	
Ethnicity	
Duration of diabetes (categorised as 0-5, 5-10, >10 years)	
BMI: Due to missingness of the data, BMI was not included as baseline	
Smoking (Yes/No)	
HbA1c (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	
Cholesterol (continuous): Due to missingness of the data, Cholesterol was not included as baseline	
Blood pressure (continuous): Due to missingness of the data, Blood pressure was not included as baseline	
Glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), based on creatinine: due to missingness of the data, eGFR was not included as baseline	
History of atrial fibrillation	
History of myocardial infarction	
History of heart failure	
History of stroke	
History of peripheral artery disease	
History of renal disease	
History of diabetic eye disease	
Concomitant glucose lowering treatment	Concomitant glucose lowering treatment
Therapy with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aldosterone receptor antagonists • Beta-blockers • Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers • Loop diuretics • Calcium channel blockers • Thiazide diuretics • Statins 	Therapy with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aldosterone receptor antagonists • Beta-blockers • Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers • Loop diuretics • Calcium channel blockers • Thiazide diuretics • Statins

Concomitant Glucose-Lowering Treatment, & Therapy included as a baseline covariate by examining the treatment 180 days before baseline and as a time-varying confounder if initiated after baseline.

2. Data preparation

We will explore the distribution of all continuous variables using relevant measures and graphs, such as measures of central tendency and variation, box plots, histograms, and Q-Q plots, to identify outliers. Any outliers found will be checked to determine if they are clinically plausible or if they are due to measurement error.

To address missing data, we will check the mechanism of missingness using formal tests like Little's MCAR test and graphical methods, such as heatmap plots. For data imputation, we will use random forest -based methods i.e. Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations Random Forest (MICE RF). Studies have shown that this method is suitable for complex epidemiological studies and can produce unbiased estimates of (log) hazard ratios. Parameter estimates are less biased using random forest MICE, and confidence interval coverage is improved.

3. Analysis

3.1 Target parameter of interest

Risk difference/ratio between taking insulin degludec for 1-2 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated), compared to taking treatment with insulin glargine for 1-2 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated).

3.2 Descriptive analyses

A series of descriptive analyses will be made. These will include the following questions using non-parametric analyses:

1. Total population studied and how many people were exposed to the insulin in question
2. How many of those people met the inclusion criteria for the study in the two arms.
3. Baseline characteristics of the two study arms
4. Calendar year of inclusion for each study arm
5. Time to administrative censoring or loss to follow-up
6. Time to treatment discontinuation, by treatment, accounting for death, emigration, and administrative censoring
7. Time to any additional add-on
8. Number of primary and secondary outcomes by initial treatment

Initially, we will calculate summary statistics for both continuous and categorical variables. Continuous variables will be described using measures of central tendency such as mean and median, and measures of dispersion like standard deviation and interquartile range. Categorical variables will be summarised with frequencies and percentages.

Baseline characteristics will be compared between treatment groups using appropriate statistical tests to assess the balance before treatment initiation. For time-varying variables, incidence rates over time

will be calculated, and Kaplan-Meier curves will visualise time-to-event data for key outcomes. After performing multiple imputations, we will compare the distribution of imputed data with the original data to ensure that imputation has not introduced bias. These descriptive analyses will provide a solid foundation for the subsequent inferential analyses, ensuring that any findings are based on a thorough understanding of the data.

To capture changes in HbA1c levels over time, we will use longitudinal graphs. These graphs will display the trends in HbA1c for both medication groups, highlighting how glycaemic control evolves during the study period. By plotting individual patient trajectories as well as group averages, we can observe the overall effectiveness and variability of each treatment. Additionally, these graphs will help identify any significant shifts in HbA1c levels that may correspond with treatment adjustments or discontinuations.

Furthermore, we will analyse prescription patterns and treatment adherence using longitudinal data. Graphs will show the frequency of treatment dropouts and switches, providing insights into patient adherence and the sustainability of each treatment strategy. These visualisations will enable us to identify common reasons for discontinuation and assess whether patients who switch treatments exhibit different clinical outcomes compared to those who remain on their initial medication.

3.3. Statistical estimation

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months. We estimate the target parameters with a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator. The estimator updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting (propensity of treatment, probability of not being censored). All nuisance parameter regression models needed for the initial estimator and for the targeting step are adjusted for additive effects of all covariates, updated to the current time interval, such that we never confuse the causal time order of the variables. Specifically, we regress the outcome/treatment/censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval $(t, t+6 \text{ months})$ on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the whole history of the treatment variables at time t . All nuisance parameter models were fitted using penalized ridge regression selecting the penalty parameters such as to undersmooth the regression fits. For continuous variables, we employ flexible modelling techniques, including linear modelling, spline-based adjustments, and categorization of continuous variables, using diverse super learners. We do not truncate propensity scores and censoring probabilities. Reported are the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals.

Longitudinal Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (LTMLE)

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months ($t=0, 6, 12, \dots, 36$) to estimate the target parameters using a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator (LTMLE). LTMLE is a robust

statistical method that accounts for time-varying covariates and treatments, providing accurate and unbiased causal effect estimates

Our data will be structured into 6-month intervals, creating a longitudinal dataset where each participant has multiple records corresponding to each 6-month period. Each record will include both time-varying covariates (e.g., HbA1c levels, incident health conditions, concomitant medications) and treatment status for that interval. Baseline covariates such as age, sex, and initial health conditions will be included as static variables.

LTMLE updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting, accounting for the propensity of treatment and the probability of not being censored using Super Learner approach. SL is an ensemble method that allows researchers to combine several different prediction algorithms into one where the candidate algorithms can be quite different. It uses K-fold cross-validation to build the optimally weighted combination of predictions from a library of candidate machine learning algorithms. The estimation procedure involves several key steps:

Model Specification

Define models for the treatment mechanism (the probability of receiving degludec versus glargine given past covariates and treatment history) and the outcome mechanism (the probability of the outcome given past covariates and treatment history).

Initial Estimates

Obtain initial estimates of the outcome and treatment probabilities using these models. All nuisance parameter regression models necessary for the initial estimator and for the targeting step will be adjusted for additive effects of all covariates updated to the current time interval, ensuring the causal time order of the variables is maintained.

Targeted Update

Apply a targeting step to adjust the initial estimates using inverse probability weights. Specifically, we will regress the outcome, treatment, and censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval (t , $t+6$ months) on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the entire history of the treatment variables up to time t .

Penalised Ridge Regression

Fit all nuisance parameter models using penalised ridge regression, selecting penalty parameters to under smooth the regression fits, which helps in reducing the bias in the estimates.

Iterative Process

The targeting step is iterated until the estimates converge, ensuring the final estimates are consistent with the observed data and the specified causal model.

Reporting and Interpretation

The primary analysis will focus on estimating the causal effect of continuous treatment with sitagliptin versus taking treatment within thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea class on the primary and secondary outcomes over the study period. We will report the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals. These estimates will provide robust and interpretable causal insights into the comparative effectiveness of sitagliptin versus thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea in real-world clinical practice.

By employing LTMLE, we address the complexities of time-varying treatments and covariates, ensuring that our analysis correctly models the dynamic nature of treatment effects and confounding factors over time. This approach will yield reliable and nuanced insights into the long-term impacts of these diabetes treatments.

3.4. Subgroups Analyses

We will stratify our analysis of the primary outcome across several key demographic and clinical subgroups. These subgroups include sex, age group, ethnicity, baseline HbA1c levels, duration of diabetes, and Index of multiple deprivation. By examining treatment effects within these subpopulations, we aim to identify potential variations in treatment response and assess the generalisability of our findings across diverse patient profiles.

When stratifying the data for the subgroup analysis, we will investigate the data for sparse data problem and amend the analysis accordingly.

3.5. Sensitivity analyses

As part of our sensitivity analysis, we will implement a grace period of 30 days by shifting the index date to day 30 after treatment initiation. This adjustment allows for a more flexible definition of treatment exposure, accounting for potential delays in treatment response or adherence variations during the initial phase of therapy. Following the adjustment, we will repeat our main analysis, including the estimation of primary and secondary outcomes, within this modified timeframe.

To investigate the possibility of confounding by indication, we will add history of hypoglycaemia as a baseline confounder and assess the differences in treatment effects on the primary outcome. This is because in the UK, when Degludec was first available it was a more expensive Insulin and justification has to be given for prescribing it; the justification was usually more severe hypoglycaemia.

By conducting sensitivity analyses, we can evaluate the robustness of our primary findings and assess the potential impact of methodological variations on our results. The inclusion of a grace period addresses potential misclassification of treatment exposure and ensures that our estimates remain valid under alternative modelling assumptions. Overall, these sensitivity analyses enhance the

reliability and validity of our study findings, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the treatment effects observed in our primary analysis.

References

1. Marso SP, McGuire DK, Zinman B, Poulter NR, Emerson SS, Pieber TR, Pratley RE, Haahr PM, Lange M, Brown-Frandsen K, Moses A, Skibsted S, Kvist K, Buse JB; DEVOTE Study Group. Efficacy and Safety of Degludec versus Glargine in Type 2 Diabetes. *N Engl J Med*. 2017 Aug 24;377(8):723-732. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1615692. Epub 2017 Jun 12. PMID: 28605603; PMCID: PMC5731244.

Appendix

Table S1- Glucose-lowering prescriptions available in NDA

Medication	ATC code*
Glucose-lowering prescriptions	
DDP-4 inhibitors	Z79.84
GLP-1 receptor agonists	Z79.84
Glucosidase inhibitors	Z79.84
Insulin	Z79.84
Meglitinides	Z79.84
Metformin	Z79.84
SGLT2 inhibitors	Z79.84
Sulfonylureas	Z79.84
Thiazolidinediones	Z79.84
Blood pressure lowering prescriptions	Z79.51 Z79.52 Z79.899 Z79.899 Z79.899
Aldosterone receptor antagonists	Z79.899
Beta-blockers	Z79.51
Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers	Z79.52
Loop diuretics	Z79.899
Calcium channel blockers,	Z79.899
Thiazide	Z79.899
Cholesterol-lowering prescriptions	Z79.02
Statins	Z79.02

*In NDA we will use SNOMED codes:

https://eur03.safelinks.protection.outlook.com/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fdigital.nhs.uk%2Fbinaries%2Fcontent%2Fassets%2Fwebsite-assets%2Fdata-and-information%2Fdata-collections%2Fqof%2Fbusiness-rules-2023-2024%2Fnda_v7.0.zip&data=05%7C02%7Csg18%40leicester.ac.uk%7C73f68d668bf94f47e7fe08dc96a4d837%7Caebeecd6a31d44b0195ce8274afe853d9%7C0%7C1%7C638550881965779184%7CUnknwn%7CTWFpbGZsb3d8eyJWIjoiMC4wLjAwMDAiLCJQIjoiV2luMzliLCJBTiI6Ik1haWwiLCJXVCi6Mn0%3D%7C0%7C%7C%7C&sdata=31BZpJPdraNvjV5w6QYo5egLXXFdWXLvJfgp7Gb3NOs%3D&reserved=0

Table S2- Secondary care data and mortality data available through linkage of the NDA

Medical Condition	ICD codes
Heart failure	I50.1, I50.20-23, I50.30-33, I50.40-43, I50.9
Myocardial infarction	I121.0-9, I122.0-9
Stroke	I61.0-9, I63.0-9, I166, I169
Peripheral artery disease	I170.20-29
Renal disease	N18.3-5, E10.2, E11.2
Diabetic eye disease	E11.319,321. 331, 341, 351, E11.321, 3211,331,3311,341,3411,351,3511, E11.39
Atrial Fibrillation	I48.0, 148.1, 148.11, I48.11, I48.19, I482, 21, 3,4,91, 92, I44.91, 92,
Hypertension	I10, I11, I11.0, 11.9
Cancer	C00-C14, C15-26, C30-39, C40-41, C43-58, C60-97
Liver disease	K70-77
Endocrine disorder except type 2 diabetes	E00-07, E15-16, E20-35
Alcohol or drug abuse	F10-19
Chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease	J40, J43, J44
Unstable Angina	I20.0-9, I24
Bariatric surgery	0DBM0ZZ
Revascularization	02703ZZ 02713ZZ, 02723ZZ 02733ZZ 02763ZZ 02773ZZ 02783ZZ 02793ZZ 02793ZZ
Mortality	
All-cause mortality	All codes
Cardiovascular mortality	